

Something to Hold on to 2

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Abstract

Just over thirty years ago, I gave a published talk ‘The Something to Hold on to Factor in Timbral Music’ (SHF, 1994) which has been evolving ever since. Given my focus as musicologist and as composer on making innovative music accessible to a broader public beyond specialists, SHF offers means to identify aspects of shared experience that can help new listeners navigate their way through electroacoustic works as well as access tools for composers. Given the combination of issues raised in the EMS25 call alongside the foci of my recent talks and composition series, it seems timely to create a sequel to this key text of mine in which the intention is to add various social and cultural aspects to the SHF that a) can make electroacoustic music accessible and, perhaps more poignantly, b) make this music more relevant in today’s world.

This assumes that electroacoustic music is communicable in a general sense. It also implies that a work can be *about* something, thus enabling an intention/reception loop as the basis of potential shared experience.

The talk will return to the original SHF reintroducing it along with publications of others who further developed it. Following this, it investigates and illustrates areas including ecology, place and (inter)cultural material related to compositional approaches to discover how all of these can support both access and social relevance.

As someone interested in sample-based composition, I have experienced using musical samples that are (inter)culturally rooted or taken from our daily lives enabling the creation of works that are both aesthetic and socially engaging. This approach will illustrate the talk’s aim of optimising intention with reception as well as the accessibility of today’s and tomorrow’s electroacoustic works offering both specialists and nonspecialists with some more things to hold on to

1. Introducing the ‘Something to Hold on to Factor’ and a Related Initiative

For those unfamiliar with my work, I have been addressing issues related to the marginalisation of experimental, especially electroacoustic music for decades and have attempted to offer means of improving this situation in both my scholarly and artistic work. One of the first contributions was launched in a conference talk given in London in 1993 and published a year later that focused on what I called the ‘Something to hold on to factor’ (SHF) in timbral music which was the conference subject. To this end I listened to over 150 CDs (the medium of the day) and analysed which aspects of electroacoustic pieces could support a non-expert’s

navigation through the works. In many cases there were none. My initial list looked as follows (1994, p. 56):

- (i) Some parameters for a start
 - (a) Dynamics
 - (b) Space
 - (c) Pitch (and rhythm)
- (ii) Homogeneity of sounds and the search for new sounds
 - (a) To begin - pieces based on one or a few pitches
 - (b) Homogeneous textures
 - (c) New sounds
 - (d) The voice and the special case of a live instrument plus tape
- (iii) Textures not exceeding four sound types at once
- (iv) Programmes, some are real but many are imaginary
 - (a) One programme - nature (for a change)
 - (b) Two special cases with recycled known sounds
 - those musical and "anecdotal"
 - (c) Acousmatic tales
- (v) And so on

The original Something to Hold on to Factor list

Given the fact that this initiative has continued to evolve and is supported by issues raised in the EMS25 call, it has now become clear that both a new item is needed involving the recycling of musical elements and sounds as well as the fourth item is deserving greater prominence and quite a bit of broadening. My notion in the 90s was that a work's dramaturgy could offer something to hold on to. My view today and this talk's plea is for people to consider making works *about* something to a) offer greater access to (and interest in participating in) sonic creativity, and b) support our music becoming more socially relevant, thus increasing both our communities of interest and of participation.

Around the millennium, a follow-up initiative called the Intention/Reception (I/R) project (Weale 2005, Landy 2006) was launched involving listeners of various backgrounds internationally. Both have been discussed at various EMS conferences and in further publications. The I/R project data has demonstrated how non-expert listeners (well, everyone in fact) seek connections with previous experience when listening to electroacoustic works. This implies that intention can meet reception supporting access when elements of shared experience can be identified.

Before going further, it should be noted that this type of connection can range from superficial to profound. Let's investigate this briefly through my notion of multiple levels of appreciation and/or understanding. Take, for example, humour in a children's animation movie. Children will laugh at moments aimed at them (as will most adults); adults will also laugh at moments aimed only at them; and, if there is a specific subject involved, specialists in that subject will laugh at jokes aimed at them, too. Analogously, Barry Truax has been known to say that soundscape compositions are best experienced by those familiar with the specific place of a work. I would suggest, applying the movie example, that, for example, a work focusing on a harbour is experienced by the third group, namely those who do know that harbour, in a certain

way. This, however, does not necessarily lessen the appreciation of those familiar with any harbour or even those who haven't been to a harbour at all but have simply experienced a water source. It will just be different.

To summarise this introduction citing this talk's abstract: the goal here is to launch a 'sequel to this key text of mine in which the intention is to add various social and cultural aspects to the SHF that a) can make this music accessible and, perhaps more poignantly, b) make this music more relevant in today's world'. To this end, those two updates to the list of things to hold on can serve to ensure connections with shared experience. Examples follow below.

2. Relating the Above to the EMS25 Call/1

I was pleased to see that this year's EMS conference call included areas such as ecology, place, urban studies, cultural and intercultural studies. This reflects a healthy blurring of boundaries that is evolving in academe and well beyond reflecting a much more inter-/cross-/transdisciplinary world. One wonders, for example, to what extent electroacoustic music can be taught in isolation today given all the audiovisual applications related to it. It is the transcending of disciplines with the socio-cultural contexts in which we live that has been highlighted by the EMS25 hosts. In an article written in 1999 in which I reviewed the state of the musicology of electroacoustic music, I wrote that the greatest 'hole in the market' of the field was what I called 'ethno-electroacoustic musicology', namely the study of this music as a cultural phenomenon. Whether this involves composing with quotidian or cultural aspects in sonic works or researching any of an abundance of socio-cultural subjects in relation to electroacoustic music and its place in culture, I would suggest that this call is timely.

Combining those areas in the call with my remarks about transdisciplinarity, an example: as editor of the journal, 'Organised Sound', it has been difficult to discern how the rapidly evolving area of sound studies fits within the field of electroacoustic music studies. The fact of the matter is that it is not a question of fit but instead of that crossing or even overlapping of disciplines that is relevant, a reflection of today's blurred boundaries.

Let's look at an ethno-EMS current issue: We are living in a time of limited experimentation and financial support whether related to education or cultural funding. Experimentation most often takes place in more comfortable times, yet I would place the present as the most uncomfortable I've ever experienced. Although electroacoustic approaches permeate audiovisual media today, are our practices in general reaching wider audiences? If not, are we running the same risk as our orchestras of potential societal redundancy as we become even more marginal than we were? I am not pessimistic about the future but do believe that discussions at EMS events and beyond about the place and function of this music are essential and, amongst these discussions, the key subject of making our music more attractive to broader audiences and participants *must* be central.

Just as in music history where many national and international schools of composers have happily coexisted, Clearly, in today's electroacoustic music world, those seeking abstraction and/or complexity obviously have their rightful place. Nonetheless, it has been proven that such approaches often do not serve our music's accessibility. Furthermore, is our presenting electroacoustic music in general as a 'high art' form an ideal *modus operandi*? Is this artform becoming overly institutionalised as time goes on? Across the broad horizon of its subgenres and categories, to what extent do our communities of interest go beyond an expert audience and

even beyond its makers? (Of course, if the community of interest is intended to consist only of its makers, it is probably best to simply state that.) These questions deserve addressing.

In my view an excellent access tool would involve moving beyond l'écoute réduite and celebrating l'écoute augmentée, seeking means of shared experience with a broader potential audience. Reduced listening suggests expert listening (mea culpa, Pierre Schaeffer). Heightened listening goes hand in hand with strong dramaturgy. Heightened listening works continue to be more exception than the rule making access more challenging. Fortunately, I believe that this pattern is slowly changing.

Heightened listening takes us to our everyday lives. We all have strong views on areas ranging from race, gender, religion, climate change, political economic policy, not to mention intercultural conflicts (which often have to do with the subjects just mentioned). These are all outstanding themes for sonic creative endeavour. Regarding the subject of addressing culture within musical creation, as an educator, I have often asked students to what extent they would like to reflect their own culture in their work. The vast majority have responded apathetically at best. Is this due to the omnipresence of commercial culture? I am no longer certain that this is the reason and am of the firm belief that addressing cultural elements, too, is an excellent means of linking intention with reception in sound offering listeners with something to hold on to.

It is true that obligation to embed one's culture as a music composition student in one's works can have a negative effect. I have experienced this in a few countries during my career. Similarly, being bombarded with one's own culture's music as government policy on mass media has a similar negative effect. Most of us do not live in cultures with such obligation and might enjoy sharing aspects of lived experience, whether in terms of musical content or subject matter, within or across our cultures. Such works are *about* something and involve a variety of levels of shared experience. Given the difficult times in which we now live, such connections can be vital as an outlet of enhancing or placing in question our lived experience and values.

To summarise: ecology, place, cultural and socio-political issues ranging from the everyday to the global are all valid foci for electroacoustic works enabling the sharing of real-life issues as sonic experiences.

3. Music Being *about* Something

As stated, the ideal presented in this talk is neither new nor unique. It is its prominence and importance that are being highlighted. In this section, a few examples of good practice are mentioned.

Events: Socio-cultural and other themes have been chosen as electroacoustic conference and festival themes beyond this one. Naming but two, in 2023 at Visiones Sonoras, the annual festival of CMMAS in Morelia, Mexico, ecology and climate change was the theme. The Balanced/Unbalanced events (in which EMS25 speaker Ricardo dal Farra is a key organiser) has the motto: 'arts + science x technology = environment/responsibility'.

Publications: The number of publications reflecting such themes investigating electroacoustic music as related to these subject areas is fortunately increasing. What might be challenging for people interested in these crossovers is where and how to find them as many such publications primarily reside in the sister subject area, not electroacoustic music studies. Those focused on sound and ecological subjects are now very easy to find and the field is expanding in breadth

and depth. This can bring in subjects such as urban studies, sociology as well as acoustic ecology and politics. In areas related to cultural and intercultural issues, both in terms of the music itself and the circumstances surrounding the music, it is my view that a great deal of development is still needed.

‘Organised Sound’ has included special issue themes such as socially engaged sound practices and ecologically grounded creative practices. There are alas still too few comparable proposals being received as well as relevant articles sent independently of such themes. Beyond sound studies and acoustic ecology journals, where might clusters of such publications reside and why does this imbalance continue to be the case?

My own written contributions commenced with pedagogical projects, such as EARS 2 (eLearning) and the book, ‘Making Music with Sounds’ (2012), and being invited by EMS25 speakers Kerry Hagan and Miller Puckett to write an analysis of a work by a composer who ‘deserved greater attention’ for their edited book, ‘Between the Tracks’ (2020). I had already wanted to learn more about Hildegard Westerkamp’s work and chose one that really was *about* something, namely ‘Beneath the Forest Floor’ (1992), a work celebrating the beauty and environmental importance of a forest in British Columbia, one threatened with decimation due to commercial logging. The composer was quite up front about her desire for this work to be about something with a political message wrapped up in the highly aesthetic journey of her piece. It is this combination that adds depth to magic and is potentially of interest to a highly diverse audience due to its content and its social statement which are both shareable. Recently, most of my writing continues to address the socio-cultural relevance of sonic creativity.

Compositions: Any student of electroacoustic music will have encountered Luigi Nono’s ‘La Fabbrica Illuminata’ from 1964 for soprano and tape regarding the exploitation of the working class and intended to be performed in factories as well as concert halls. It was most likely the first important political piece of electronic music. How much impact it had on workers is a story probably better left untold. Was this the reason why political electroacoustic music has been the exception to the rule? I have my doubts. I believe it was more to do with the combination of the then aesthetic of electronic music combined with its high art ethos.

Ironically, one group of unsung heroes of our history are sound artists. Sound installations and what followed are by no means new. Many sound art works are situated in their specific environment and many of these are also about something. Whilst electroacoustic music avoided such connections, sound art embraced them often facilitating shared experience. Soundscape composition evolved in parallel with the field of acoustic ecology and with few exceptions its works are all about something or somewhere. From this, groups interested in field recordings have evolved and much of their work is equally socially engaged. Given that these examples remain part of a minority of electroacoustic production, I suggest that the acousmatic curtain might have been the cause of the destiny of much electroacoustic work.

I would now like to share one of my favourite stories regarding my career as composer, in which I have frequently made sample-based compositions, which in turn enables works to offer shared experience. The story takes place in Amsterdam. I had loved pinball machines (flipper in many European languages) since I was a child. and had a mechanical one when I was young, too. Although ‘Tommy’ the ‘pinball opera’ by The Who was already famous (during the talk, the piece was played under my speaking from here), I had the idea of making a piece, indeed a political piece made solely from recordings of the ubiquitous pinball machines at the time, 1980. I was given permission by a pinball hall to arrive prior to its opening one day recording

individual machines and continued to do so when the hall was open to its customers when a ‘pinball wizard’, a young Moroccan boy who probably should have been at school, started playing pinball virtuosically alongside those engaged with other machines. I paid for a few of his games and kept recording. My idea was to create a ‘Boléro for pinball machines’. Once my dramaturgy was set and I’d categorised my source materials, I decided to start the piece with a relatively quiet mechanical machine, have it play throughout the piece and be the only sound that remains at the end, long forgotten under the mayhem of amplified electronic ones. The piece was given the title, ‘What’s Left?’, an ambiguous one I leave to you to think about. Whilst preparing the materials in the evenings at the studio of the University of Amsterdam where I worked at the time, only the Turkish cleaner was present. We’d treat each other to tea but hardly spoke, until ... On the day I mixed three stereo recordings into the final master mix, I was unaware that he was waiting out in the corridor. When I finished, he offered me tea and asked what I was doing. I told him I was making a piece. He responded with the non sequitur of my life: ‘Do you know my cousin?’ I replied, ‘I don’t think so’. He said he was a butcher living and working in Hilversum. I asked whether he was doing well, and his response was: yes, his business was doing well, and his goal was to purchase a hotel in his region of Turkey to support his family. I said that this was great. However, he continued, his cousin was spending his money on fruit machines and the like, and he was virtually penniless. He asked for a cassette copy of my piece to play it at Turkish cultural centres in Holland as a warning of the risk of addiction to these machines. My piece ended up with a stronger dramaturgy than the one I imagined due to what I have been calling ‘shared experience’.

More recently, I have been focusing on cultural preservation in a series called Old/New in which forms of world music threatened with potential extinction are shared for their beauty and dynamic across time. The piece performed later today belongs to this series focusing on both the richness and dynamic of two types of Chinese traditional instruments whilst crossing cultures by way of a European performer and composer both fascinated in Chinese culture. In a separate series, I have recomposed several countries’ radio broadcasts to demonstrate universal, national and regional aspects alongside our socio-political themes of the day to allow surrealism and humour to place our daily lives in question. In both series, I am attempting to offer multiple levels of shared experience whilst addressing much broader audiences than our expert one. as a form of what I call ‘a theatre of sound in a choreography of space’.

There is, however, a danger with the use of samples worthy of mention. This is to do not only with the inevitable subject of rights of use but also regarding cultural sensitivity. I have often purported that samples should only be used with respect to the original culture unless there is a good reason to do otherwise (think of the current US President). They should not be treated as sonic postcards or used without knowledge of their original function or meaning. An example I return to often is a track on the original LP ‘My Life in the Bush of Ghosts’ (1981) made by Brian Eno and David Byrne in which an imam is reciting from the Koran. They created a riff around it. It was withdrawn from the LP’s second release as they neither had the rights to that recording nor did they show respect to Islam infuriating those involved and many others. Shared sonic experience should therefore take cultural sensitivity into account.

4. Relating the Above to the EMS25 Call/2 (Conclusion)

It is clear how much breadth there is for music and scholarship to address the world around us, celebrating and crossing cultures, reflecting issues of the day and also reflecting many artists’

views that the point of art is to challenge society! Three decades after having formulated the original things to hold on to, doesn't the concept of offering people, not only sonic things to hold on to but also culturally and socially relevant ones make sense? We need to understand this opportunity better, both the socio-cultural context of our work and its musical and cultural potential.

To this end, I have updated the SHF's main categories where two have been highlighted. Number ii is new and SHF's number iv (now v) 'Programmes: some are real and many are imaginary' should now read 'Real-life issues, cultural elements and programmes' which would include several subcategories as we have now seen. The SHF is of clear relevance to musicians thinking about their potential audience and thus the relevance of their work as well as to scholars including the entire EMS community as it opens electroacoustic music studies to applied areas of great importance.

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| (i) | Some parameters for a start |
| (ii) | <i>Musical, cultural and everyday recycled sounds</i> |
| (iii) | Homogeneity of sounds and the search for new sounds |
| (iv) | Textures not exceeding four sound types at once |
| (v) | <i>Real-life issues, cultural elements and programmes</i> |
| (vi) | And so on |

The Something to Hold on to Factor Headers Updated

Therefore, to conclude, I return to the talk's abstract: 'those subjects listed in the call are applicable paths for optimising intention and reception as well as accessibility of ... electroacoustic works offering nonspecialists with something to hold on to within today's and tomorrow's sonic creativity'.

5. References

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